

A Comprehensive Review of RP-HPLC In Bioanalytical Method Validation and Sample Preparation

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ABSTRACT

Bioanalytical method development is essential for the accurate quantification of drugs and their metabolites in biological matrices such as plasma, serum, or urine. Techniques like liquid-liquid extraction (LLE), solid phase extraction (SPE), and protein precipitation are commonly used to isolate analytes from complex biological samples. Among various analytical tools, HPLC is widely preferred due to its speed, specificity, accuracy, and precision. HPLC is especially suitable for analysing low dose drugs and multicomponent formulations, making it a critical component in pharmaceutical research and development. Method development and validation are vital at all stages of drug discovery and manufacturing to ensure that analytical procedures are fit for their intended purpose. Regulatory bodies require validated methods for various stages of drug development, including Investigational New Drug (IND) applications, New Drug Applications (NDA), and Abbreviated New Drug Applications (ANDAs). Validated HPLC methods support pharmacokinetic and toxicokinetic studies, which are essential for assessing drug safety and efficacy. This article focusing on parameters such as selectivity, sensitivity, linearity, precision, accuracy, and stability. The development of robust HPLC methods contributes significantly to the success of new drug applications and ongoing pharmaceutical research.

Keywords: High Performance Liquid Chromatography, Bioanalytical, Validation, Method development, etc

INTRODUCTION

1. High Performance Liquid Chromatography

HPLC is powerful and widely used approach for isolating, determining, and measuring particular components in a liquid mixture. [1] When assessing new formulations, monitoring reaction changes throughout synthesis processes or scale up, verifying the peak purity of novel chemical entities, and performing quality control and assurance on the finished drug products, HPLC is the preferred technique. [2] It is a more advanced form of a liquid chromatography that uses high pressure to move a solvent (the mobile phase) through a stationary phase packed column. HPLC has isolated each individual chemical component from the sample mixture based on its unique affinities for the mobile phase or adsorbent substance in the column, causing various constituents to separate in the column, causing various constituents to separate as they travel at different velocities. [3]

1.1 Principle

HPLC works on the basis of separating components interactions with a stationary phase as they get carried by a mobile phase. Small particle size of stationary phase which gives high surface area to make separation more specific and precise. The use of micro syringes allows samples to be injected into pumps that provide high pressure flow of the mobile phase. [4] When small volume of analyte is injected into column the components will move with different affinity in column and separate out with different retention time and on recorder will give distinct and resolved peaks which is used in analysis of analyte. [5]

1.2 Classification of HPLC can be done as [6]

HPLC is often divided into two subclasses according on the mode of operation:

A. NP-HPLC

Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

The term “Normal Phase High Performance Liquid Chromatography” (NP-HPLC) refers to methods where the mobile phase is less polar than the stationary phase. In NP- HPLC SiO₂, NH₂, -CN, NO₂, ALO₃ and diol are used as stationary phase and cyclohexane [7-8]

B. RP-HPLC

In RP-HPLC mobile phase used is polar or slightly polar, but the SP is non polar. Separation is primarily based on hydrophobic interactions. [9] Non-polar analytes in the polar mobile phase are attracted to and interact effectively with non-polar SP, leading to

longer retention. Polar analytes have weak interactions with the SP and elute quickly as they are more soluble in the polar MP. [10]

1.3 Instrumentation

The common parts of HPLC instrumentation are

1. Solvent reservoir
2. Pumps
3. Sample injector
4. Column
5. Detector

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of HPLC

1. Solvent reservoir

A reservoir made of glass holds the contents of the mobile phase. The polar and non- polar liquid components that make up the mobile phase, or solvent, in HPLC are often mixed together, and the amounts of these components vary based on the sample’s makeup. Usually polar and non-polar solvents are stored separately in different container and used in proper ratio in isocratic and gradient elution. [11-12]

2. Pumps

Pumps are designed to prevent pulsation during the change in composition of mobile phase. HPLC pump continuously pump the mobile phase towards the column with constant pressure and constant flow rate of pump may up to 200 bar depending upon flow rate. Depending on needs of the analysis, the operational pressure limits can vary greatly, ranging from 2000 to

5000 psi in normal analytical operation. [13-14] Three commonly used pump types are

- **Constant pressure pump:** This uses pressure from a gas cylinder to generate a steady, continuous flow rate across the column. The solvent chamber can be quickly refilled due to the valve configuration. To produce high liquid pressures, a low-pressure gas source is required.
- **Syringe type pump:** The column receives the steady flow rate through a controlled anchor mechanism. Adjusting the motor’s voltage determines the solvent supply rate. Significant drawbacks include restricted solvent storage and restricted gradient operation.
- **Resiprocating piston pump:** These uses the rotating action of a piston in a hydraulic chamber to deliver the solvents. Because one pump is in the delivery cycle and the other is in the filling cycle, reciprocating pump systems provide smooth

solvent supply. Both gradient operation and high pressure output at a consistent flow rate are achievable.

3. Sample Injector

Sample injector used to add the sample to the active mobile phase. Liquid samples with a volume of 0.1-100 mL can be loaded into an HPLC injector with excessive pressure (in the range of to 4,000 psi) and satisfactory reproducibility. When a user has to detect a more number of samples, an auto sampler is an automatic version. Samples are injected into the mobile phase stream at a fixed volume using injectors. To maintain a high degree of accuracy, injection must be inert and repeatable. [15-16] The sample can be introduced into the injection port in three crucial ways.

- **Loop Injection:** In this type, fixed volume loop injector is used to introduce a fixed quantity of volume.
- **Valve Injection:** This makes an use of an injection valve to introduce an alterable volume.
- **On column Injection:** In which, a syringe is used to insert a varied volume through a septum.

4. Column

Made mostly of clean stainless steel, columns have internal dimensions of 2 to 5 mm in width and 50 to

300 mm in length. Columns are packed with a SP that contains particles between 3 to 10 μm . Microbore columns have internal diameter of less than 2 mm. During the analysis, maintaining a constant temperature for both the column and the MP is adequate. [17] Various column types are- 1) Guard columns and 2) Analytical columns [18]

Guard column: It prolongs the lifespan of analytical column by eliminating impurities and particulate, matter from solvents. It has same composition compared to analytical column, but it has large particle size.

Analytical column: It is referred to as heart of HPLC, as from it mobile phase continuously passes. The length of column can be vary from 10 to 30 cm with diameter of 4 to 10 mm.

5. Detector

Every molecule that elutes from the chromatographic column can be identified by the HPLC detector. The detectors include electrochemical, ultraviolet spectroscopy, mass spectrometric, fluorescence, and evaporative light scattering detectors are utilized. Detector supplied an output from the detector to a computer or recorder, which produces the graph, or a liquid chromatogram of the detector output. Both the necessary sensitivity and a particular response are provided by a detector for the components that the column separates. [19]

Table 1: Detector and their applications

	Detector	Analytes	Solvent requirement
1	UV Visible	Any with chromophores	UV grade non-UV absorbing
2	Fluorescence	Fluorescent	UV grade non-UV absorbing solvents
3	Refractive index (RI)	Compound with a different RI to that of mobile phase	Cannot run mobile phase gradients
4	Conductivity	Charged/ polar compounds	Mobile phase must be conducting
5	Mass spectrometer (MS)	Broad range of compounds	Must use volatile solvent and volatile buffers

1.4 Application of HPLC [20]

1. Pharmaceutical application

HPLC has a high linear dynamic range and reliable quantitative precision and accuracy, it can be used to

quantify various substances in a single run. A useful method for preparing samples for solid dosage forms in aqueous solutions that have been altered with acetonitrile or methanol. There are several ways to separate chiral substances into their respective

enantiomers using HPLC. Precolumn derivatization is one method of creating diastereomers.

2. Manufacturing

There are several uses for HPLC in experimental and therapeutic science. This technique is commonly used in pharmaceutical manufacturing as it is an accurate way to determine and confirm the purity of the product. HPLC is not often the primary method used in the production of bulk pharmaceutical compounds, although its ability to yield very pure and superior products. Unfortunately, HPLC tends to increase specificity, precision and accuracy at the expense of increased cost.

3. Research [21]

Research may determine the concentration of potential medicinal candidates, such as asthma drugs and antifungal treatments, using similar assays techniques. When attempting to determine the identify of a species, this method necessitates the use of standard solutions, because purity is crucial in research, it is employed as a technique to verify the outcomes of synthesis procedures. It is definitely useful in observing a variety of species in sample collection also.

4. Medical

Drug analysis is one application of HPLC in medicine, but it is more closely related to nutrient analysis. The most common medium for detecting medication concentrations is urine, but usually medical analyses utilizing HPLC use blood serum as the sample. Other techniques, such as immunoassays, for detecting chemicals that are relevant for clinical research has been evaluated against HPLC. In one instance, the sensitivity of HPLC and competitive protein binding assays (CPBA) for vitamin D detection was evaluated.

6. Foods

High-performance liquid chromatography has improved food analysis in ways that are desired. In general, food matrices are complicated, and extracting analytes is a challenging process. Trace elements often contain both unwanted and useful components, and conventional separation and evaluation

techniques are not accurate or precise enough to make matters more problematic.

1.5 System Suitability Parameters

A crucial component of the liquid chromatographic approach is a system suitability test. They are used in analysis to make sure that the chromatographic system has adequate resolution and reproducibility. The test's foundation is the idea that the apparatus, electronics, investigative process, and tester under analysis form a single, integrated system that should be assessed as such. [22] System performance before or during analysis is confirm by determining the parameters such as resolution, plate count, reproducibility and tailing factor. [23]

A. Retention time (RT)

Retention time is the interval of time between the injection site and peak maximum appearance. Additionally, it can refer to the time it takes for half of a component to come out from a column. The measuring units are minutes and seconds.

B. Theoretical plates (N)

An alternative name for it is column efficiency. Wherever the distribution of the tester between liquid-liquid or solid- solid segment takes place, a column can be seen of as consisting of a large no. of theoretical plates. To determine TP formula is given below:
$$N = 16 \left(\frac{RT}{W} \right)^2$$

Where RT= Retention time and w= Width at the peak's base.

As the no. of TP in a column rises, it increases its separation efficiency. Efficient separation results in clear, well-defined peaks, and improved resolution between distinct analytes. There should be more than 2000 theoretical plates.

C. Resolution

Resolution, as used in HPLC analysis, is the chromatographic system's capacity to isolate and differentiate between two neighboring peaks in a chromatogram. The precision and dependability of the analytical results are directly impacted by this

parameter, making it an essential one in HPLC. Using the following formula, the resolution (R) between two neighboring peaks is determined:

$$R = \frac{2(t_2 - t_1)}{w_1 + w_2}$$

Where w_2 and w_1 = Widths at the bases of the 2 & 1 peak, respectively.

while t_1 and t_2 = Retention times of the 1 and 2 compounds, respectively.

D. Tailing Factor

The tailing factor (TF), a numerical quantity that measures the amount of tailing in an HPLC peak, is used to evaluate the peak shape of a chromatographic peak. It is computed using the following formula:

$$T = \frac{W_{0.05}}{2F}$$

Where F is the length of the peak height from the baseline to the peak maximum, and $W_{0.05}$ is the peak's width at 5% height. A totally symmetrical peak is represented by a TF of 1, whereas tailing is indicated by values greater than 1 and fronting is shown by values less than 1. [24]

E. Selectivity (α)

This measure of peak spacing is sometimes referred to as the separation factor and is written as

$$\alpha = \frac{K'_2}{K'_1}$$

Table No.1: HPLC parameters and standard acceptance range

Sr.no.	Parameters	Acceptable range
1.	Theoretical plates (N)	>2000
2.	Resolution (Rs)	>2
3.	Tailing Factor (TF)	≤ 2
4.	Peak asymmetry (As)	1

2. Analytical method development using RP-HPLC

Analytical techniques are always being created, refined, verified, jointly researched, and used. These created techniques are subsequently compiled in sizable compendia like USP, BP and IP, among others. Usually, it just takes a few attempts to get the necessary separation. Typically, method development entails choosing the method requirements and determining the kind of instrumentation to use and

why. During the HPLC method development phase, choices for detectors, mobile phase, column, and method quantitation must be made. The optimal stationary phase, column, detector, internal diameter for columns, and mobile phase all be selected when creating n new HPLC techniques. This is because development involves consideration of all characteristics related to any method. There are several steps in the analytical strategy for developing an HPLC method, as seen figure 3. [25-26]

Figure 2: Flow Chart for Method Development by RP-HPLC

3. Bioanalytical method development

Analytes in certain biological fluids, including blood plasma, serum, or urine, are measured quantitatively. Pharmacokinetic and toxicokinetics studies are conducted both clinically and non-clinically to assess the safety and effectiveness of drugs. Using

bioanalysis to assess characteristics in vivo interactions between drugs, bioavailability, and bioequivalence. The examination of analytes and their metabolites, endogenous compounds, and biomarkers from biological fluid is done using a bioanalytical approach. [27]

Figure 3: Procedure for bioanalytical method development

3.1 Sample Preparation

Aim of sample preparation is to extract analyte from the biological matrix, which can be injected into the chromatographic apparatus. Techniques for preparing

drug and metabolite samples from biological sources traditionally, the following extraction procedures are used to isolate the analyte from the biological tissue. [28]

Figure 4: Sample preparation techniques

3.1.1 Liquid extraction (LLE)

The foundation of LLE is analyte molecules partition equilibria and varying solubility between the aqueous and organic phases. A substance's transition from one liquid phase to another is commonly referred to as liquid liquid extraction. LLE is regarded as being inexpensive and capable of producing clean extracts and good analyte recoveries. LLE technique is a widely used sample preparation technique in regulated biological analysis. It may be necessary to acidify, basify, or use small amounts of more polar solvents in the extraction process in order to simultaneously obtain high recoveries for the primary analyte, metabolites, and related chemicals. [29]

Procedure: The component mixture should be dissolved in an appropriate solvent first, and then an

immiscible solvent should be added. To create layers of the two immiscible solvents, properly mix the ingredients and set aside. Based on the partition coefficients of the two immiscible solvents, the mixture's constituent parts will be divided between them. After separating the two layers of immiscible solvents, move and separate the component from each solvent. Hydrophilic substances enter the aqueous phase after extraction, while hydrophobic compounds are found in the organic solvents. By letting the solvent evaporate and then reconstituting the residue with a tiny amount of a suitable solvent, ideally mobile phase, non-polar analytes that have been extracted into the organic phase can be readily recovered. A reverse phase (RP) column can be directly filled with polar analytes that have been extracted into the aqueous phase. [30]

Figure 5: Liquid extraction

3.1.2 Solid Phase Extraction (SPE)

In SPE technique in the analyte is eluted selectively after being attached onto a solid substrate and interferences are removed. Conditioning, sample loading, washing, and elution are the four stages that make up the solid phase. It has evolved as a powerful technique for the extraction and measurement of analyse trace components in various sample matrices. The main goal of SPE are sample concentration, removal of contaminants and interfering compounds, and retention and elution of analytes from biological fluid. [31-32]

Steps involved in SPE

1. Conditioning

To condition or equilibrate the cartridge or column, the sorbent is moistened with a solvent in the first stage of SPE. It shows that an organic solvent, a wetting agent for packing materials, is used to activate

the cartridge or column. For the proper adsorption process to begin, water or an aqueous buffer is supplied to the column.

2. Loading

The subsequent step involves percolation through the solid phase of the loading solution that that contains the analyte. The sorbent thus retains the analytes and some impurities. The samples are neither pumped, vacuumed, or gravity fed into the column once the pit has been fixed.

3. Washing

The sorbent is cleaned to remove impurities. While the matrix interference is removed, the analytes are kept intact.

4. Elution

The final stage, the elution step, involves collecting the analytes.

Figure 6: Solid phase extraction

3.1.3 Protein precipitation

Proteins are routinely removed from analyses using protein precipitation. The process through which proteins in a biomatrix lose their tertiary and secondary structures- known as denaturation- is caused by external stressors such as heat, strong acids

or bases, or common organic solvents like methanol or acetonitrile. A quick and simple extraction method for both water loving and water repelling compounds is protein precipitation. Sometimes, to gain higher efficiency protein precipitation technique combine with LLE or SPE for the purpose of extraction of particular medicines and metabolites. [33]

Figure 7: Human plasma extraction procedure

3.1.4 Micro-extraction technique

Modern extraction techniques like micro extraction usually result in an extremely small proportion of extracting solvent to sample volume and minimal analyte separation. One effective and relatively recent method for sample preparation is micro extraction. Some advantages of using micro extraction techniques in bioanalysis include high rates of sample preparation, enhanced efficiency of extraction, small sample quantity, accuracy, reduced solvent intake, and a reduced expense. [34]

4. Bioanalytical Method Validation

According to FDA guidelines, validation is the process of producing a registered proof that provides a high degree of assurance that a particular operation will consistently produce a product that satisfies its predetermined parameters, quality specifications, and quality attributes. All of the steps necessary to show that a specific bioanalytical method for the quantitative assessment of an analytes (or group of analytes) concentration in a given biological matrix is dependable for the intended use are included in bioanalytical method validation. A minimum set of validation trials and satisfactory outcomes provide reassurances regarding the method's reliability and accuracy. [35]

4.1 Need of Bioanalytical Method Validation [36]

- To provide accurate data that can be completely accepted, it is important to implement

bioanalytical techniques that have been fully explained and validated.

- Bioanalytical methods and techniques are at the top of technology and are known to be constantly developing and improving.
- It is important to remember that every bioanalytical technique has special characteristics that differ from one analyte to another and that each analyte may require a different set of validation criteria should also be implemented.
- In addition, the study's final goal may have an impact on the techniques suitability. When analysis of samples for specific research is carried out at different location, inter- laboratory reliability must be established by validating the bioanalytical methods at every site and providing appropriate validation data for different locations.
- Since the properties of the bioanalytical technique differ from analyte to analyte, it could be necessary to define distinct validation criteria for every analyst.
- The bioanalytical techniques produce accurate and satisfactory results.
- Validation is proving that the technique's performance characteristics are appropriate and reliable for the proposed analytical applications through the use specific laboratory investigations.

4.2 Parameters of Method Validation [37-38-39]

Analytical method validation is the process to produce results from tests consistently and continuously fulfil predefined criteria. Method validation is the process of verifying that the investigative technique being

used for a particular test is appropriate for its intended use. An essential element of any valid study procedure, process validation results can be used to

assess the quality, consistency, and dependability of results. All validation parameters are described in this section.

Figure 8: Bioanalytical Validation Parameter.

1. Accuracy

The degree to which a measured value approaches the true or accepted value is known as accuracy. In practical terms, accuracy shows the difference between the actual value and the mean value found. The degree to which test results obtained using an investigative methodology closely resemble the actual value is known as technique's accuracy. Pure standards of dapagliflozin and vildagliptin at three different concentration levels (80%, 100% and 120%) were added to the tablet sample solution that had been previously analysed in order to evaluate accuracy. At each level, the average recovery should be between 99 and 101% of the drug.

2. Robustness

Robustness is a measure of an analytical technique's ability to maintain accuracy even after deliberate minor adjustments to its parameters. A techniques robustness is a measure of how sensitive it is to minute changes in temperature, pH levels, mobile phase composition, and other variables that could occur during routine analysis. Systemic adjustments were made to the mobile phase composition, wavelength, and flow rate (± 0.1 ml/min) to maximize robustness. RSD was used in the calculation.

3. Linearity

The International Council for Harmonization (ICH) has given a definition, an analytical method's ability to produce test results that accurately reflect an analyte concentration within a specific range is known as its linearity. To determine the linearity, one can utilize the correlation coefficient. In order to do this evaluation, three to six different standards must be injected at concentrations that ranges from 80% of the lowest expected level to 120% of the highest predicted level, or in ranges like 50-150% or 100-120%.

4. Precision

The degree of agreement between a set of measurements made by repeatedly sampling the same homogenous sample under specified conditions is expressed as the precision of an analytical method, which is a measure of the chance of error. There was precision research investigations conducted both inside and between days. Three distinct drug concentrations were injected into a single intraday precision sample, and a chromatogram was recorded. Similarly, to do inter-day precision analyses, three distinct amounts were injected, and a chromatogram was acquired over the course of two consecutive days. The percentage of coefficient of variance (CV%), or

the ratios of standard deviations (SD) to the mean, was used to calculate the intraday and inter-day testing precision.

$$\%CV = \frac{\text{Standard Deviation}}{\text{Mean}} \times 100$$

5. Limit of Detection (LOD)

It is the lowest detectable but not usually quantifiable concentration of an analyte in a sample. The analysis process and instrument type will determine the detection limit. The detection is commonly expressed as a percentage or parts per billion (ppb) of the test specimen's analyte concentration.

$$LOD = \frac{3.3 \times \text{Standard deviation}}{\text{Slope}}$$

6. Limit of Quantification (LOQ)

Lower limit of quantification (LOQ) is the smallest amount of a material in a sample that can be measured with acceptable precision and accurately below a technique's predefined operating parameters. LOQ is an empirical measure of compounds that are found in sample matrices in extremely small amounts, like breakdown products in commonly used therapies and contaminants in bulk medications. The signal-to-noise ratio, standard deviation, and visual assessment

techniques are some of the methods used to determine LOQ

$$LOQ = \frac{10 \times \text{Standard Deviation}}{\text{Slope}}$$

7. Reproducibility

"Reproducibility" describes how accurate a procedure is when there are changes in the laboratory, including different days, analysts, and equipment. Each testing site can prepare a total of six sample preparation in accordance with the analytical procedure. Additionally, the results are analysed to ensure statistical consistency across different testing sites. The same approval criteria that apply to intermediate precision also apply to reproducibility.

8. Ruggedness

According to USP, "the ruggedness of an analytical method is denoted by the extent of reproducibility of test results obtained by the analysis of the same samples under a variety of normal test conditions, such as different labs, different analysts, temperature, assay labs, instruments, and different reagents. "Ruggedness is a metric that quantifies a method's responsiveness to minor variations that may arise during normal analysis, such as slight variations in temperature, mobile phase composition, or pH values.

Table 2: Acceptance criteria for method validation as per ICH guidelines.

	Parameter	Standard values
1	Accuracy	Recovery 98-102%
2	Precision	RSD < 2%
3	Repeatability	
4	Robustness	
5	Detection Limit	S/N > 2 or 3
6	Quantification limit	S/N > 10
7	Linearity	Correlation coefficient- NLT 0.999
8	Range	80-120%
9	Specificity	Interference < 0.5%
10	Ruggedness	Should meet all system suitability parameters

5. Application of RP-HPLC in drugs by analysis utilizing different sample preparation techniques.

Sr. No	Analyte	Bio-matrix	Sample preparation	Stationary phase (Column)	Extraction solvent	References
1	cinnarizine and domperidone	Rat plasma	PPE	C18 Sunfire (5 μ m, 250 mm \times 4.6 mm)	Acetonitrile	40
2	Thiocolchicoside + Lornoxicam	Human plasma	PPE	C18 (5 μ m, 250mm \times 4.60mm)	Acetonitrile(60 0 μ l)	41
3	Docetaxel	Human Plasma	LLE	C8 (4.6 \times 250 mm)	acetonitrile	42
4	glimepiride	rat plasma	LLE	Phenomenex C18 (150 \times 4.6 mm, 4 μ m)	Deep eutectic solvents	43
5	Ticagrelor	Human plasma	PPE	C18 (250 X 4.6 mm, 5 μ m)	Diethyl ether	44
6	Favipiravir	Human plasma	LLE	C18 (250 X 4.6 mm, 5 μ)	Ethyl acetate	45
7	curcumin and quercetin	Rat plasma	PPE	RP C18	acetone & ACN (1:1)	46
8	linagliptin and metformin	Human plasma	PPE	Grace vyadyec genesis CN (150 \times 4.6 mm, 4 μ m)	Acetonitrile	47
9	Clopidogrel bisulfate	Human plasma	PPE	C18 (250 \times 4.6 mm, 5 μ)	methanol	48
10	Rufinamide	Rat plasma	PPE	Kinetex C18 (250 \times 4.6 mm, 5 μ m)	disodium EDTA	49
11	Lenvatinib	human plasma	LLE	zodiasil C18 (150 \times 4.6 mm, 5mm)	acetonitrile	50
12	Remdesivir	human plasma	LLE	ChromosilC18 (250 X 4.6 mm, 5 μ) column	Diethyl ether & methanol (50:50)	51
13	Sofosbuvir	human plasma	LLE	Kromasil Column (250 X 4.6 mm, 5 μ m)	Acetonitrile	52
14	Chlorthalidone and Cilnidipine	human plasma	PPE	Inertsil C18, (150 \times 4.6 mm; 5 μ m)	acetonitrile	53
15	Resveratrol	rat plasma	LLE	Kinetics C18 (250 \times 4.6 mm, 100 Å pore size, and 5 μ m)	Methyl tert-butyl ether	54
16	Rimonabant	Human plasma	LLE	Hypersil BDS, C18 (250 mm \times 4.6 mm; 5 μ m)	Ethyl acetate:n-hexane (70:30)	55
17	Vardenafil	Human plasma	LLE	Eclipse XBD-C8 ((150 mm \times 4.6 mm \times 5 μ m)	Diethyl Ether	56
18	Tadalafil	Human plasma	LLE	XBD-C8 Plasma ((150 mm \times 4.6 mm \times 5 μ m)	Diethyl Ether	57
19	Teneligliptin	Rabbit plasma	LLE	Thermo C18 (100 mm \times 4.6 mm \times 5 μ)	Ethylacetate	58
20	Dapagliflozin	Rat plasma	PPE	C18 (4.6 x 250mm, 5 μ particle size)	Ethyl acetate	59
21	velpatasvir and sofosbuvir	Human plasma	LLE	Intersil ODS C18 ((250 mm \times 4.6 mm \times 5 μ m)	Ethyl acetate	60
22	ledipasvir and Sofosbuvir	Human plasma	LLE	Oyster BDS RP-C18 (5 μ m, 250 mm X 4.6 mm)	Diethyl ether & dichloromethane (60:40)	61
23	Lercanidipine and Atenolol	Human plasma	LLE	Phenomenox Gemini C18 (150mmX4.6, 5 μ)	Tert-butyl methyl ether	62

24	Ifenprodil	Rat plasma	PPE	Luna Phenyl hexyl (150 mm × 4.6 mm, 3.5 μm)	Acetonitrile	63
25	Nebivolol and valsartan	Human plasma	PPE	C18	acetonitrile	64
26	Levocetirizine	human plasma	LLE	Prontosil C-18 (4.6 x 250mm, 5μ particle size)	Acetonitrile	65
27	Paracetamol and Cefixime	rabbit plasma	PPE	ODS C18 ((250mmx4.6mm, 5μm)	Acetonitrile	66
28	Metformin	Human Plasma	PPE	ZORBAX Eclipse Plus C18 (4.6 x 100 mm, 3.5μm)	acetonitrile	6
29	Telmisartan	Human Plasma	PPE	Hibar C18 (250 x 4.6 mm, 5 μm)	methanol	68
30	verapamil and enalapril	Human Plasma	PPE	C18 (50 × 2.1 mm, 5 μm)	acetonitrile: methanol (50:50)	69
31	Remogliflozin etabonate	human plasma	PPE	THERMO C18 (250×4.6 mm, 5 μm)	acetonitrile	70
32	Carvedilol	Rat plasma	PPE	Agilent C18 column (4.6 x150 mm) 5 μ	methanol	71
33	Edaravone	human plasma	PPE	Thermo C18 (250 x 4.6 mm i.d.5μ)	Trichloro acetic acid	72
34	Raloxifene	Rat plasma	LLE	C18 (15 × 4.6 mm, 5 μm)	ethyl-acetate	73
35	Nebivolol hydrochloride	Rat plasma	LLE	Knauer C18 (250 X 4.6 mm, 5μ)	acetonitrile & methanol (1:1)	74
36	lopinavir	Rat plasma	PPE	C8 (150 mm × 4.6 mm i.d, particle size 5μ)	Acetonitrile	75
37	Pethidine hydrochloride	Human plasma.	PPE	HyperClone (Phenomenex®) C18 (250 × 4.6 mm id, particle size 5 μm, ODS 130 Å)	Acetonitrile	76
38	Zidovudine	Human plasma	LLE	Phenomenex C18 (250×4.6 mm i.d., 5 μm)	Methyl-t-butyl ether	77
39	Daunorubicin & Cytarabine	Blood Plasma	PPE	Prontosil C-18 (4.6 x 250mm, 5μ particle size)	Acetonitrile	78
40	Valsartan	Rat plasma	PPE	ODS C18 (4.6 × 250 mm, 5 μm,)	Acetonitrile	79

CONCLUSION

High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) remains a cornerstone in bioanalytical method development due to its reliability, precision, and suitability for complex drug formulations and low-dose compounds. These various essential development and validation characteristics for bioanalytical methodology have been discussed with a view to improving the standard and acceptance in this area of research. Techniques such as LLE, SPE,

and protein precipitation enhance the efficiency of sample preparation, enabling precise analysis even in complex biological systems. By focusing on essential parameters like selectivity, sensitivity, linearity, precision, accuracy, and stability, researchers can develop robust analytical methods that contribute significantly to the advancement of safe and effective pharmaceutical therapies. Applications of bioanalytical method in routine drug analysis are also taken into consideration in this article. This review provides a general overview of HPLC bioanalytical

method development and validation. The optimized method is validated using various parameters (e.g., specificity, precision, accuracy, detection limit, linearity, and so on) following ICH guidelines.

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HOW TO CITE: Kiran Ukey*, Indrajeet Gonjari, Pratiksha Rajguru, Kajal Bansode, Rugved Sathawane, Jayashri Dandale, A Comprehensive Review of RP-HPLC In Bioanalytical Method Validation and Sample Preparation, *Int. J. Sci. R. Tech.*, 2025, 2 (6), 270-286. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15606059>